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Scientific Schools of the Kharkiv State Academy of Culture through the Prism of Google Academy Scientometrics

Objective. The article aims to highlight the role and importance of officially recognized scientific schools at the Kharkiv State Academy of Documentary and Information Culture using data from Google Scholar. The research was conducted during July-August 2024. **Methods.** The study employs scientometric analysis as the main method for determining the current state of science and technology in the field of social communications, alongside methods of analysis and synthesis. The analysis method was used to study the scientific literature on the research topic, the professional development path of the leaders of the scientific schools of the Kharkiv State Academy of Culture, and the terms used in the study. The synthesis method was used to write the conclusions of the research. **Results.** The results of the analysis of scientometric profiles of the leaders of these scientific schools in Google Scholar are presented. The study also establishes the expediency of using scientometric analysis of profiles in Google Scholar to determine the state and trends in the development of scientific fields and industries. **Conclusions.** The article demonstrates the potential of analyzing scientometric profiles of researchers in Google Scholar to assess their overall scientific productivity and the nuances of achievements at different stages of research activities in the field of social communications.

Keywords: scientific school; scientometrics; researchers; Kharkiv State Academy of Culture; scientific productivity; social communications

Introduction

A scientific school is typically considered a community of scientists with varying statuses and competencies, united by their commitment to the theories and ideas of a leader in a specific discipline. It fulfills all functions of scientific activity, including knowledge production through research, dissemination, and reproduction.

A significant place in this network is held by the modern scientific schools of the Kharkiv State Academy of Culture, the oldest higher education institution in Ukraine with a focus on library and information studies. It is well known that contemporary disciplines within the social and communication cycle are built on a solid foundation of theoretical achievements from their predecessors. Scientific ideas, concepts, and paradigms – distributed across time and space – experience a renaissance through scientific communication (both formal and informal, verbal and non-verbal, direct and indirect). Over time, these ideas are updated, becoming fruitful over the centuries and contributing to our understanding of the laws and patterns of theoretical thought evolution, as well as the contributions of individuals and scientific schools to its development. This allows us to outline the prospects for the advancement of documentary and information structures in society, as well as in sectoral science, education, and management within the modern social and communication landscape.

Today, the Kharkiv State Academy of Culture officially recognizes 10 scientific schools, four of which focus on documentary and information studies: The Scientific School of Documentation, led by Nataliia Kushnarenko; the Scientific School of Library and Information

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Studies, led by Alla Solianyky; the Scientific School of Social Communications and Documentary Information Systems, led by Iryna Davydova; and the Information and Documentation Scientific School, led by Liudmyla Filipova. Analyzing the scientometric profiles in Google Scholar of the leaders of these schools may serve as an indicator for assessing the state and trends in the development of library and information science.

Literature review

Significant scientific achievements of the Kharkiv Library and Information School are well documented in the professional literature, particularly regarding its origins, development, and the key figures among its founders and prominent representatives. Notably, the fundamental monographs regularly published to commemorate the anniversaries of the Kharkiv State University of Library and Information Science are especially significant, particularly “Fundatory Kharkivskoi bibliotechnoi naukovo-osvitnoi shkoly”, which is dedicated to the founders of the Kharkiv Library and Information Science School (Solianyky, 2019).

The origins and development of the Kharkiv library school in the early part of the last century are explored in works by R. Drahan (2000) and V. Siedykh (Siedykh & Shcherbinina, 2011). Researchers have also examined specific scientific areas within the Kharkiv school, such as the contribution of the Kharkiv Bibliography School to the development of Ukrainian bibliography (Todorova, 2011) and the importance of the Kharkiv Scientific Documentary School (Kokhanova, 2011). Additionally, studies have focused on particular aspects of the Kharkiv Library and Information School, including the identification of scientific schools in cultural, artistic, and library information profiles (Sheiko, Kanistratenko, & Kushnarenko, 2011), as well as historical and communication aspects (Kushnarenko, 2011) and the system of communication links (Sheiko, Kushnarenko, & Solianyky, 2012).

It is noteworthy that the role and significance of the Kharkiv Library and Information School and some of its representatives have been analyzed using bibliometric methods (Kobieliev, 2001) and biobibliometrics (Kobieliev, Karpenko, & Kolesnykova, 2023). However, no comprehensive studies on the scientometric profiles of the leaders of the officially recognized documentary and information science schools at the Kharkiv State Academy of Culture have been found in Google Scholar. This gap underscores the relevance of the current study, particularly given the increasing importance of scientometric indicators in modern scientific activity.

Taking into account the above, we believe the purpose of this article is to highlight the role and significance of the officially recognized scientific schools of Documentary and Information Studies at the Kharkiv State Academy of Culture by analyzing the profiles of their leaders on Google Scholar.

Methods

The activities of scientists and their social connections can be revealed through scientometric analysis of bibliographic data. The research was conducted during July-August 2024. In addition to the scientometric method, the method of analysis was used, in particular, when studying the scientific literature on the research topic, the professional development path of the leaders of scientific schools of the Kharkiv State University of Arts and Sciences, and the terms used in the study. The method of synthesis was used in writing the conclusions of the study. This paper presents the results of a comparative scientometric analysis of the profiles of the leaders of

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officially recognized scientific schools at the Kharkiv State Academy of Culture and Documentary Information, as reflected in Google Scholar.

Achieving this goal requires a preliminary consideration of the essence of scientometrics and its applications in studying the scientific work of prominent scientists, both individually and as part of scientific schools. Therefore, in the Results and Discussion section, the authors have identified two subsections: «The Essence of Scientometrics» and «Results of the Scientometric Analysis of Scientific Schools of Kharkiv State Academy of Culture».

Results and Discussions

The Essence of Scientometrics

Scientometrics is a branch of science that deals with the statistical study of the structure and dynamics of scientific information. This term is often used synonymously with bibliometrics, webometrics, and informetrics. The object of scientometrics is the scientific sphere of society, while the subject of study involves expert evaluation and forecasting of research activities based on monitoring scientific communications. The main task is to analyze publication activity and citation patterns of authors of scientific papers.

The methods of scientometrics are quantitative, including bibliometric analysis, citation indices, probabilistic and statistical methods, and expert evaluation. Key issues in scientometrics encompass the information model of scientific development, the growth of information flows, citation indices of scientific literature, the study of internal relations in science based on bibliographic references, assessment of individual countries' contributions to the global scientific information flow, and statistical analysis of scientific areas.

The term «scientometrics» was introduced into scientific discourse in 1969 by V. Nalimov in the monograph *Scientometrics: The Study of the Development of Science as an Information Process*, co-authored with Z. Multchenko. In this work, it was proposed to define scientometrics as the quantitative method of studying the development of science as an information process. Ukrainian scientists have made significant contributions to both the theoretical and practical developments in the field of scientometrics. A particularly important work for the advancement of scientometric research, even before V. Nalimov, was the monograph *Science of Science: Introduction to General Science* (1966) by G. Dobrov, who later became the founder and head of the Center for Research of Scientific and Technical Potential and the History of Science of the Academy of Sciences of the Ukrainian SSR. This work contributed to the intensification of interest in scientometrics as a practical tool for science studies and has been translated into many languages (Kobieliev, 2001).

Today, based on new theoretical concepts and perspectives, it becomes both possible and necessary to consider and address the problems of defining and interacting with the aforementioned areas of quantitative research, founded on the existence of documentary, informational, and cognitive levels of communicative relations in society. The latter, as noted, is «expressed in the presence of documentary, informational, and cognitive structures within the social communication system» (Ilhanaieva, 1996, p. 59). It is these structures that determine the existence of corresponding distinct areas of quantitative analysis.

Therefore, it is appropriate to consider bibliometrics as a quantitative method at the documentary level, informetrics at the informational level, cognimetrics as a promising method of quantitative analysis of knowledge related to the cognitive level of social communications, and

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scientometrics as a distinct quantitative method that combines data provided by the aforementioned three methods with its specific indicators.

Regarding scientometrics in general, one can agree with M. Morales' view that scientometrics is not a system of scientific and technical information and documentation, but rather a designed construct of knowledge that should enhance this system (Morales, 1985).

Thus, in works dedicated to determining the level of scientific development, not everything is reduced (or should be reduced) to informational aspects, although, as mentioned above, scientometrics was initially defined as a quantitative method for studying science as an informational process. This is because scientometrics measures not the patterns of information and communication, but rather the objective quantitative indicators that truly define the achieved level.

Examples of such scientometric indicators may include the number of scientists; the number of inventions; the economic impact of new technologies; the volume of contracts for the sale or purchase of licenses, know-how, etc. (Kolesnykova, 2020). However, as already emphasized, scientometrics also utilizes quantitative data on the informational aspects of scientific activity provided by bibliometrics and informetrics, meaning that there exists an area of mutual overlap between these disciplines.

After the scientific revolution of the first half of the 20th century, which revealed the limitations of existing ideas about objective reality, there was a shift from an abstract methodological concept to the study of scientific schools, research groups, and collectives (Syniakov, 1998). More adequate research methodologies began to be actively developed. Their most important feature is a decisive rejection of the cumulative model of scientific development. In other words, it was demonstrated that every discovery results from a complex interaction of socio-cultural, institutional, and everyday circumstances.

Furthermore, as noted, «modern science is embedded in a multitude of socio-cultural contexts» (Toulmin, 1972, p. 65). A detailed analysis of specific situations (such as conferences, debates, and correspondence among scientists) reveals that the development of science is not deterministic; from any given point, it could have followed different paths (Kolesnykova, 2020). For instance, scientists might not recognize a certain fact as a scientific achievement and, as a result, could begin to pursue alternative research programs.

Thus, this situation takes on the meaning of a unique event – prepared but not predetermined by the past. The nature of this preparation largely depends on the tasks and methods of the researcher, which may reveal a clash of interests among various scientific groups or a revival of old philosophical disputes. As Toulmin observes, «An intellectual discipline develops through successive historical phases defined by different sets of concepts, problems, and assumptions». To «trace the intellectual development of a discipline», it is necessary to «identify the different galaxies of absolute assumptions» in the field of interest and to «determine their similarities and differences» to identify which features change and which remain constant across historical phases (Toulmin, 1972).

Consequently, one of the most important features of modern science studies is the focus on the detailed examination of everyday scientific life – the functioning of research laboratories, the dynamics of scientific schools, and the relationships among scientists and their surrounding communities.

In conclusion, a characteristic feature of science research in recent decades has been the emergence of the subject of scientific activity – those who create scientific knowledge—as the focal point in methodological analysis. This is because «scientific knowledge is loaded with various socio-cultural components and the relationships that develop between scientists in the process of creating ideas, hypotheses, and concepts» (Syniakov, 1998, p. 74).

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In recent years, more attention has been paid in Ukraine to research activities, which are becoming a priority for higher education institutions, large libraries, museums, archives, and others. One significant outcome of this trend is the formation and successful long-term operation of scientific schools. The importance of these schools is further underscored by the fact that scientific specialties are similar to other social organizations. They also have their own 'reference' groups, consisting of individuals whose choices eventually lead to a professional path. A new concept, theory, or strategy 'enters' a scientific discipline only when it is taken seriously by influential representatives of the relevant scientific field.

Results of Scientometric Analysis of Scientific Schools at the Kharkiv State Academy of Culture

In the twentieth century, the primary units of scientific activity were scientific communities that generated new knowledge based on the division and cooperation of labor, as well as the routinization of processes involved in knowledge creation, transfer, and application. One form of such a scientific community is a scientific school – an association of researchers that functions to produce and disseminate new knowledge while possessing the ability to self-reproduce.

The essential characteristics of scientific schools typically include:

- a common object of research and a unified paradigm of scientific activity;
- the ability to generate knowledge that distinguishes this school from other groups;
- proprietary technologies for creating, transferring, and applying knowledge;
- the manifestation of self-development effects based on the exchange of results and ideas both within a single generation and between teachers and students;
- recognition by other scientific fields.

The relevance of studying scientific schools is underscored by their contribution to the advancement of science. As history shows, they serve not only as mechanisms for involving individuals in the production and consumption of knowledge but also as unique centers of concentrated creative energy.

The objective prerequisites for establishing and developing a scientific school generally include the presence of a scientist with a strong scientific reputation; scientific circles; conferences and round tables on specialized topics; publication of monographs, textbooks, and manuals that foster the formation of new professional knowledge in the field; the availability of master's, postgraduate, and doctoral programs; the defense of candidate and doctoral dissertations; and generational continuity.

As noted by Sheiko, the creation and development of a scientific school is a long, costly, and highly complex process. Scientific schools act as custodians of the best scientific traditions of their universities, passing these traditions on through their students to other research teams and the broader community (Sheiko, Kushnarenko, & Solianyk, 2012).

Typically, a scientific school is officially recognized by the most reputable scientists in the relevant field. Notably, the establishment of a scientific school does not require a specific organizational structure (such as departments or laboratories). It may comprise scientists from various departments, faculties, laboratories, institutes, and research organizations.

The above factors, along with the realities of higher education, allow us to conclude the following main features of scientific schools:

- the presence of a leader who possesses a keen perception of emerging trends in science and practice, as well as organizational skills to create a creative team of like-minded individuals;
- generational continuity;
- the acquisition of objectively new knowledge that enriches science.

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All these criteria are met by the scientific schools of documentary and information studies at the Kharkiv State Academy of Culture (Table 1).

Table 1

Contemporary officially recognized scientific schools in document and information studies at the Kharkiv State Academy of Culture

No.	Name of Scientific School	Leader of Scientific School
1	Scientific School of Documentology	KUSHNARENKO Nataliia Mykolaivna, Professor of the Digital Communications and Information Technologies Department, Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor, Honored Worker of Arts of Ukraine
2	Scientific Library and Information School	SOLIANYK Alla Anatoliivna, Professor of the Digital Communications and Information Technologies Department, Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor
3	Scientific School of Social Communications and Document-Information Systems	DAVYDOVA Iryna Oleksandrivna, Professor of the Digital Communications and Information Technologies Department, Doctor of Social Communications, Professor, Academician of the National Academy of Sciences of Higher Education of Ukraine
4	Scientific Information and Document School	FILIPOVA Liudmyla Yakivna, Professor of the Digital Communications and Information Technologies Department, Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

As is well known, the most common method in scientometrics is the bibliometric method of scientific citation, based on the Science Citation Index. This index serves as a widely accepted indicator of a scientist's work significance, represented by the number of citations of their scientific papers. The Science Citation Index has many derivatives. For instance, the Hirsch index (h-index), proposed in 2005 by physicist H. Hirsch from the University of California, San Diego (USA), is one of the primary scientometric indicators that reflects the influence of a scientist, a team of scientists, a scientific institution, or a scientific journal, based on the number of publications and their citations.

This data can be obtained, among other sources, from a profile on Google Scholar. Its main advantage (Strochenko, 2020) is that it is a freely available search engine that indexes the full text of scientific publications across all formats and disciplines, allowing users to easily conduct extensive searches of scientific literature. With a single query form, users can search across various disciplines and sources, including peer-reviewed articles, dissertations, books, abstracts, and reports published by scholarly publishers, professional associations, higher education institutions, and other academic organizations. Google Scholar enables researchers to find studies that closely match their search queries among a vast number of scientific papers.

Google Scholar classifies articles similarly to how scientists do, evaluating the full text of each article, its authors, the publication in which it appeared, and the frequency of citation of that work in scientific literature. The most relevant results are always displayed on the first page.

The Scientific School of Documentation at the Kharkiv State Academy of Culture is headed by Professor Natalia Kushnarenko, Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences and Honoured Worker of Culture of Ukraine. She has been with the Kharkiv State Academy of Culture since 1972, progressing from lecturer to professor and holding various positions, including department head,

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dean of the faculty, and vice-rector for scientific, pedagogical, and educational work. She defended her PhD thesis in 1979 on the topic ‘Coordination of Acquisition of Library Collections in the Conditions of Centralisation of the Network of State Mass Libraries’ and her doctoral thesis in 1993 in the specialty ‘Book Science, Library Science, Bibliography’ on the topic ‘Library Local History: Theoretical and Methodological Aspects’. In 1996, she was awarded the academic title of professor, and in 1999, she was designated an Honoured Worker of Culture of Ukraine.

Natalia Kushnarenko has organized over 40 scientific and practical conferences at international, national, and regional levels. She is the author of more than 400 publications, including 11 textbooks and manuals that have been repeatedly reprinted, 6 monographs, and over 300 articles, reviews, teaching materials, and abstracts. Her scientific achievements are reflected and confirmed in her profile on Google Scholar, <https://scholar.google.com.ua/citations?hl=uk&user=6gh3ANcAAAAJ> (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Natalia Kushnarenko's profile in Google Scholar

The Library and Information School of the Kharkiv State Academy of Culture (KhSAC) is headed by Professor Alla Solianyk, Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, and current Vice-Rector for Research. She has been with KhSAC since 1985, progressing from lecturer to professor and holding positions as head of the department and dean of the faculty. Her PhD thesis focused on ‘Local Mandatory Copy of Documents: History and Current State of Library Supply’ (1995), and her doctoral thesis addressed the ‘Document Supply System of Ukrainian Library Collections: Theoretical and Methodological Aspect’ (2006). Alla Solianyk has authored over 300 publications, including five monographs and numerous textbooks and scientific articles. Her scientific achievements are reflected and confirmed by her profile in Google Scholar, <https://scholar.google.com.ua/citations?hl=uk&user=k1SKMjgAAAAJ> (Fig. 2).

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Fig. 2. Alla Solianyk's profile of in Google Scholar

The Scientific School of Social Communications and Documentary Information Systems at the Kharkiv State Academy of Culture is led by Iryna Davydova, Professor, Doctor of Science in Social Communications, and Academician of the National Academy of Sciences of Higher Education of Ukraine. Her professional career has been closely tied to the KhSAC, where she has worked for over 40 years. She earned her Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences degree from the Kyiv State Institute of Culture (1997) and became the first Doctor of Science in Social Communications in Ukraine (2008), with a doctoral research topic on “Information Policy of Ukrainian Libraries: Content and Development Strategies in the Information Society” (2008). Iryna Davydova has risen from lecturer to professor and has held various roles, including department head, academic secretary, and deputy chair of specialized academic councils for doctoral and PhD thesis defenses. She has published over 180 scientific works. Her achievements are reflected and confirmed by her profile in Google Scholar, <https://scholar.google.com.ua/citations?hl=uk&user=nb6PpIwAAAAJ> (Fig. 3).

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Fig. 3. Iryna Davydova's profile of in Google Scholar

The Information and Documentation Science School of the Kharkiv State Academy of Culture is led by Liudmyla Filipova, who has been part of the Academy since 1980. Over the years, she has held various roles, including lecturer, senior lecturer, associate professor, and professor in departments such as branch bibliography, informatics, information technology, and information and documentary systems. Additionally, she has served as Head of Department and Dean of Faculties.

After completing her doctoral studies at the Kharkiv State Academy of Culture in 1999, she defended her dissertation titled "Bibliographic Systems of Ukraine in the Information and Computer Space: Theory, Organization, Technology." With over 260 publications to her name, her scientific contributions are documented in her Google Scholar profile, <https://scholar.google.com.ua/citations?hl=uk&user=HVzcEzIAAAAJ> (see Fig. 4).

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Fig. 4. Liudmyla Filipova's profile in Google Scholar

The scientometric comparative analysis of the Google Scholar profiles of leaders from the officially recognized scientific schools in documentary and information studies at the Kharkiv State Academy of Culture has yielded interesting results (Table 2). Modern science relies on the principle that scientific results should be shared with colleagues, as this is essential for ensuring their impact on research processes. Studying citation dynamics reveals and measures the influence of research results on the scientific community and their usefulness to other scientists.

Citation rates are not designed to measure the inherent quality of a work without considering its context within the scientific field. Instead, they serve as indicators suggesting that a given work is likely to be significant, thereby enhancing traditional qualitative assessments and making them more objective (Kobieliev, 2001). Bibliographic references exist at the intersection of two systems: the cognitive (conceptual) system and the system of scientific recognition. Each citation is influenced by these systems. The cognitive system establishes the necessary conditions for citation. As Cozzens (1989) notes, a publication must possess scientific significance: the ideas presented should be relevant to the target audience, logically connected, and persuasive. The text of a scientific publication represents the author's effort to position ideas within a context that can affect readers differently. Bibliographic references are a crucial fragment of a scientific publication, carrying a certain «energy» of influence on the reader.

Both systems – the conceptual and the scientific recognition systems – require bibliographic references to fulfill two tasks:

- presenting the exact content of the cited publication and the precise set of concepts conveyed through accurate citation;
- providing an accurate list of cited documents.

An analysis of the Google Scholar profiles of the leaders of scientific schools at the KhSAC suggests that the publication data in this scientometric database generally aligns with the names

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and scientific schools under study. Notably, all leaders, except for Natalia Kushnarenko, exhibit similar citation statistics, including h-index and i10-index (Table 2).

Table 2

Comparative analysis of Google Scholar profiles of leaders of scientific schools at the Kharkiv State Academy of Culture

Leader of Scientific School	Citation Statistics	h-index	i10-index	Top 7 Publications by Citation	Themes (Based on Titles) of Top 7 Publications
Nataliia Kushnarenko	3129	18	27	Textbooks	Research activities, document studies, scientific processing of documents, library fund studies, local studies in librarianship
Alla Solianyuk	535	13	14	3 textbooks, 1 monograph, 3 articles	Document flows and arrays, library fund studies, document supply for library collections, social media in library internet strategies, document studies, library and information education
Iryna Davydova	627	11	18	Monograph, dissertation abstract, 5 articles	Library production, innovative library policies, theory of library activities, social media in library internet strategies, communicative-communication paradigm, bibliography, information products and services
Liudmyla Filipova	713	13	19	Textbook, 6 articles	Information analytics, electronic document circulation, documentary communications, library websites, information-communicative potential of the internet, information activities, documentary-electronic communications

The significantly higher metrics of Nataliia Kushnarenko can be attributed to her inclusion of multidisciplinary textbooks from various years and not only from Ukraine («Organization and Methods of Research Activities», «Documentation Science»), which broadens her potential audience.

The results of this analysis also confirm the thesis (Kobieliev, Karpenko, & Kolesnykova, 2023) regarding the important role of monographs in the library and information sphere. In two of the four analyzed profiles, monographs rank among the top seven cited publications. Notably, Iryna Davydova's monograph not only leads in citation ranking but significantly outpaces other works. Interestingly, the second-highest citation in Iryna Davydova's profile is her doctoral dissertation abstract, which, along with the citation data for her doctoral monograph, strongly indicates the relevance of her doctoral research.

Conclusions

The results of the scientometric analysis of Google Scholar profiles of leaders from the officially recognized scientific schools in documentary and information studies at the Kharkiv State Academy of Culture confirm the practical importance of reference analysis, along with other bibliometric and scientometric methods, for addressing a wide range of problems across various fields of science. For instance, scientometric analysis of specific document flows and their bibliometric modeling enables a comprehensive characterization of sectoral development, facilitating both quantitative and qualitative assessments.

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Moreover, reference analysis, in conjunction with other scientometric methods, is essential for many information products and services developed by documentary and communication structures. Scientometric databases, such as Google Scholar, can be viewed as expert systems. Unlike traditional large information systems that provide information to a broad audience with moderate intellectual input (e.g., abstract compilation), or costly expert systems tailored for narrow fields with limited users, scientometric databases are cost-effective and accessible to the global scientific community.

Thus, there is significant untapped potential for employing scientometric and bibliometric methods not only in domestic historical, library, and biographical research but also in the information and analytical activities of libraries. This is particularly crucial for optimizing library management processes under current financial and logistical constraints. Furthermore, scientometric and bibliometric research are vital components of many library information products and services. Therefore, there is an objective need for a research tool that facilitates the generation of results, which can serve as a foundation for further, more detailed research using traditional content analysis methods within various modern concepts and models.

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Наукові школи Харківської державної академії культури крізь призму наукометрії Гугл-академії

Мета. Стаття має на меті висвітлити роль та значення офіційно визнаних наукових шкіл Харківської державної академії культури документно-інформаційного спрямування за використанням даних Академії Google. **Методика.** У дослідженні використано наукометричний аналіз як основний метод визначення сучасного стану науки і техніки у сфері соціальних комунікацій, а також методи аналізу та синтезу. **Результати.** Представлено результати аналізу наукометричних профілів лідерів зазначених наукових шкіл у Google Scholar. Встановлено доцільність використання наукометричного аналізу профілів в Академії Google для визначення стану та тенденцій розвитку наукових напрямів і галузей. **Висновки.** У статті продемонстровано потенціал аналізу наукометричних профілів дослідників у Google Scholar для оцінки їхньої загальної наукової продуктивності та особливостей досягнень на різних етапах дослідної діяльності у сфері соціальних комунікацій.

Ключові слова: наукова школа; наукометрія; дослідники; Харківська державна академія культури; наукова продуктивність; соціальні комунікації

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